

MODIFICATIONS OF CONSONANTS IN CONNECTED SPEECH

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ANNOTATION

This article deals with the analyzing modifications of consonants in connected speech.

KEY WORDS: - assimilation, accommodation, elision, inserting, alveolar, loss of plosion, nasal plosion, lateral plosion.

There are different types of sound modification in modern English, which characterize consonants, vowels, or both. Consonants are characterized by the following types of sound modifications: assimilation, accommodation, elision, and inserting.

Assimilation the adaptive modification of a consonant by a neighbouring consonant in the speech:

1) the alveolar [t], [d],[s], [z], [l], [n], followed by the interdental [D] / [T] sounds (partial regressive assimilation when the influence goes backward from a “later” sound to an “earlier” one) become dental.

For example, at the desk.

2) [t], [d] become post-alveolar under the influence of the post-alveolar [r] (partially regressive assimilation).

For example, try, dry, that right rule, the third room. The sonorant [r] after the voiceless [t] is partially devoiced.

3) [s], [z] become post-alveolar before [S] (complete regressive assimilation)

For example, horse-shoe [hLSSH], this shop [DIS'SPp], does she [dASSJ].

4) the combinations [t+j], [d+j] tend to be affricative (incomplete regressive assimilation).

For example, graduate [grxGVeIt], did you [dIGH], could you [kVGH], congratulate [kqn'grxCVleIt].

The place of articulation of nasals also varies according to the consonant that follows.

For example, camp [m] remains bilabial before another bilabial as well as in man before a vowel.

cent [n] is alveolar before another alveolar as well as in net. symphony [m] is actually labio-dental followed by the labio-dental [f].

seventh [n] becomes dental, before the interdental [T].

pinch [n] is palato-alveolar corresponding to the following affricate [C].

thank [n] assimilates to the velar consonant becoming velar [N].

The manner of articulation is also changed as a result of assimilation, which may be illustrated as follows:

1. Loss of plosion. In the sequence of two plosive consonants the former loses its plosion.

For example, glad to see you, great trouble, an old carpet. (partial regressive assimilation)

2.Nasal plosion. In the sequence of a plosive followed by a nasal sonorant the manner of articulation of the plosive sound and the work of the soft palate are involved, which results in the nasal character of plosion release.

For example, garden, mad Mary, not now, let me see. (partial regressive assimilation)

3.Lateral plosion. In the sequence of a plosive followed by the lateral sonorant [l] the noise production of the plosive stop is changed into that of the lateral stop.

For example, people, little, at last. (partial regressive assimilation)

The voicing value of a consonant may also change through assimilation. This type of assimilation affects the work of the vocal cords and the force of articulation. In particular voiced lenis sounds become voiceless fortis when followed by another voiceless sound:

a) Fortis voiceless / lenis voiced type of assimilation is best manifested by the regressive assimilation in such words:

For example, newspaper (news [z] + paper), gooseberry (goose [s] + berry); grammatical items: [z] of has, is, does changes into [s], and [v] of have, of becomes [f] -She's five, of course, you've spoiled it, she has fine eyes, Does Pete like it?

b) The weak forms of the verbs is and has are also assimilated to the final voiceless fortis consonants of the preceding word thus the assimilation is functioning in the progressive direction.

For example, your aunt's coming, What's your name? (partial progressive assimilation)

c) English sonorants [m, n, r, l, j, w] preceded by the fortis voiceless consonants [p, t, k, s] are partially devoiced.

For example, smile, snack, tray, quite, plan, price. (partial progressive assimilation)

In English assimilation usually results in changing voiced lenis consonants into voiceless fortis.

For example, of course [qf'kLs]

Accommodation denotes the interchange of "vowel + consonant type" or "consonant + vowel type", for example, some slight degree of nasalization of vowels preceded or followed by nasal sonorants: never, men; or labialization of consonants preceding the vowels [o], [y] in Russian: кофе, больше, думать, лучше.

Lip position may be affected by the accommodation, the interchange of consonant + vowel type. Labialization of consonants is traced under the influence of the neighbouring back vowels (accommodation).

For example, pool, moon, rule, soon, whose, cool.

It is possible to speak about the spread lip position of consonants followed or preceded by front vowels [i:], [i].

For example, tea – beat, meat – team, feet – leaf, keep – leak.

The position of the soft palate is also involved in the accommodation. Slight nasalization as the result of prolonged lowering of the soft palate is sometimes traced in vowels under the influence of the neighbouring sonants [m] and [n].

For example, and, morning, come in, mental.

Elision or complete loss of sounds, both vowels and consonants is often observed in English. Elision is likely to be minimal in slow careful speech and maximal in rapid relaxed colloquial forms of speech and marks the following sounds:

1. Loss of [h] in personal and possessive pronouns he, his, her, him and the forms of the auxiliary verb have, has, had is wide spread.

For example, What has he done? ['wPt qz I· "dAn]

2. [l] tends to be lost when preceded by [L].

For example, always ['LwIz], already [L'redI], all right [L'raIt].

3. Alveolar plosives are often elided in case the cluster is followed by another consonant.

For example, next day ['neks 'deI], just one ['GAs'wAn], mashed potatoes ['mxS pq'teItEVz]

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